

Liquid-liquid extraction of rare earth elements (total) using 2,3-dihydroxynaphthalene as an extractant and its applications to the determination of REEs (total) in rock, soil and sediment samples by spectrophotometry

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Abstract : A simple and rapid separation procedure for the determination of total rare earth elements (lanthanides) including yttrium in geological samples such as rock, soil and sediments has been developed. Lanthanides form 1 : 3 complex with O-O' type bi-dentate ligand, 2,3-dihydroxynaphthalene (2,3-H₂ND) and are extracted in the ethyl acetate from aqueous solution at pH >8. Lanthanides from organic phase are quantitatively and selectively stripped off at pH 6.3 ± 0.2 followed by its spectrophotometric determination using arsenazo-III.

The effects of different experimental parameters such as pH of aqueous solution, concentration of 2,3-H₂ND, electrolytes, equilibrium time, stripping agents, diverse ions etc. on the quantitative recoveries of lanthanides were studied in detail. The percentage recovery was checked by analyzing lanthanides in synthetic mixtures and it was found that more than 98% recovery of lanthanides was obtained by this method. The accuracy of the method was ascertained by analyzing some Certified Reference Materials (CRM) like syenite sample (SY/3) and gabro sample (MRG-1). The lanthanide values obtained for the CRMs were in excellent agreement with the recommended values, indicating that the method yields fairly accurate and the reproducible results as characterized by a relative standard deviation (RSD) of 1 to 5% (n = 4). The method was successfully applied to silicate rock, soil and sediment samples.

Keywords : Lanthanides, 2,3-dihydroxynaphthalene (2,3-H₂ND), solvent extraction, spectrophotometry.

Introduction

Rare earth elements (REEs) are a group of 17 chemically similar metallic elements which includes scandium, yttrium and the lanthanides. The rare earth elements occur together in nature in some minerals like bastnasite, monazite, xenotime and others. These metal ions have been used for additives to steels or alloys, permanent magnets, hydrogen storage materials, magneto-optic storage discs, electro or cathode ray luminescence, household batteries etc.^{1,2}. Therefore, in addition to the primary sources such as the commercial enriched ores of the above referred minerals, wastes such as spent catalysts, super-alloy scrap, spent batteries, sludge, dusts etc. are the potential secondary sources of rare earths.

In geology, the REEs data are useful to understand the origin of metamorphic and secondary rocks, the oxidizing and reducing environment during rock formation,

etc. It is also useful in marine geochemistry. In petrography and in ore deposit studies, the distribution of trace elements plays a major role in the formation of ore bodies. In view of the chemical similarities, the rare earth elements, as a group, serve as indicator elements in petrogenic studies.

The determination of REEs in geological samples is one of the most difficult tasks due to complicated matrix effects. In addition, due to small difference in the chemical properties of REEs, their individual determination by classical methods such as gravimetry, volumetry and spectrophotometry³ has become uphill task. Hence, the alternative instrumental techniques used for REEs determination includes Flame-Atomic Absorption Spectrometry⁴, Graphite Furnace-Atomic Absorption Spectrometry⁵, X-Ray Fluorescence⁶, DC Arc Emission Spectrography⁷, Neutron Activation Analysis (NAA)⁸, EMPA⁹, Inductively

Coupled Plasma Atomic Emission Spectrometry (ICP-AES)¹⁰, Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry (ICP-MS)¹¹. Although strong claims are often made for the sensitivity and selectivity of ICP-AES, ICP-MS and NAA, some of the interferences to which these methods are subjected, are poorly understood and continue to cause problems. Moreover, availability of these techniques is limited due to expensive equipment and higher running cost.

On the other hand, for the determination of rare earth elements as total, spectrophotometry is a relatively easy alternative method which provides some advantages like simplicity and moderate cost. Among the various chromogenic agents reported for the determination of REEs, most of them were found to be nonselective involving serious interferences from the diverse ions. Hence, removal of closely associated metal ions like uranium, thorium and zirconium are essential due to their similar behaviors prior to determination by spectrophotometry.

Various methods have been adopted for separation of REEs which includes co-precipitation such as hydroxide-fluoride, hydroxide-oxalate with different carriers¹², ion exchange chromatography¹³, solid phase extraction¹⁴, adsorption^{15,16}. Most of the above cited separation methods except the ones based upon solid phase extraction and adsorption which are comparatively simple techniques, are lengthy and cumbersome. But solvent extraction has been used extensively over the years because of its simple operation. Using this technique, several extractants have been developed with the various organic ligands. There are innumerable solvent extraction techniques involving many organic reagents particularly organo-phosphorous compounds. Amongst these, tri butyl phosphate (TBP) and di-(2-ethylhexyl) phosphoric acid (D₂EHPA)¹⁷ are well known. Besides these, several other extractants like 8-quinolinols¹⁸, β -diketones¹⁹, *N*-phenyl hydroxylamine²⁰, 2-thenoyltrifluoroacetone²¹, and pyrocatechol and its derivatives²² are also reported.

2,3-Dihydroxynaphthalene (2,3-H₂ND) is a well known non-innocent O-O' type bi-dentate ligand. It has been used as an extractant for several metal ions like uranium, niobium, iron, titanium, manganese, molybdenum, vanadium, thorium and rare earth elements²³⁻²⁵. Earlier worker²⁵ had studied the ion-associate extraction of lanthanides (Pr³⁺, Eu³⁺, Yb³⁺) with the cited reagent from the weakly

acidic solution (acetate buffer pH) with zephiramine (benzyltrimethyltetradecyl ammoniumchloride) as a counter cation to increase the hydrophobicity of the chelate. They had observed that a certain portion of Yb³⁺ (approx. 5-10%) was extracted at this pH of 4-5 in the absence of counter cation, but they had not conducted their study in alkaline medium and its application to real samples like rock, soil, minerals etc. in order to study the effect of interfering elements during solvent extraction. Since no work on the reactions of lanthanides with the cited reagent in alkaline medium is reported till date, this prompted us to extend this application in alkaline medium with this cited reagent with special reference to the extraction stoichiometry, separation factors and the role of counter cation.

Earlier workers²⁵ have used a mixture of Na⁺ ion and benzyltrimethyltetradecyl ammonium chloride (zephiramine) as counter cation in the extraction of REEs from acidic solution. However, unlike their work, in the present work the authors could quantitatively extract REEs (total) from alkaline medium without the use of any counter cation.

In this current work, an attempt has been made to establish a method to separate rare earth elements particularly from uranium, thorium and zirconium in geological samples (silicate rock, soil and sediment) by solvent extraction using the extractant, 2,3-dihydroxynaphthalene (2,3-H₂ND) followed by its spectrophotometric determination using arsenazo-III.

Instrumentation :

An Analytik Jena (Model : SPECORD 250+), Germany double beam UV-Visible Spectrophotometer controlled by a computer was used for the measurement of absorbance with 1 cm path length quartz cell. The pH values were measured with a pH meter supplied with combined electrode (Model : L1-120), ELICO, Hyderabad, India. The flame photometer (Make : ELICO, Hyderabad, India) was used for determination of alkali metals. A calibrated electronic balance (Make : Sartorius) was used for sample weighing.

Standard solution and reagents :

Alfa Aesar' make Specpure® standard solution of lanthanides (1000 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) were used to prepare a mixed standard stock solution (100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) for investigation. The

working mixed standard solution (10 µg/ml) was prepared by diluting the mixed standard stock solution with distilled water.

Unless otherwise stated, all reagents used were of analytical grade/ guaranteed grade of standard make. The glasswares used were of grade A or class A. The water used for solution preparation in all the experiments was obtained from **Infusil** make triple distilled water plant.

Sample dissolution procedures of silicate rock, soil and sediment samples :

A 1.0 g rock or soil sample was ashed at 600 °C in the furnace to destroy organic matter. Then the sample was digested with 1 ml nitric acid and 5 ml hydrofluoric acid in a Teflon beaker on a hot plate with occasional stirring and evaporated to dryness. This procedure was repeated twice. Then 1 ml nitric acid was added and evaporated to dryness. Repeated this nitration once more and the dried mass were digested with 50 ml distilled water containing 3 ml nitric acid for half an hour. The solution was filtered and the residue, if any, was fused with sodium peroxide in a nickel crucible and the melt was dissolved in distilled water with little nitric acid. Neutralized this with diluted ammonia solution and was mixed with the mother solution maintaining 3% (v/v) nitric acid.

Extraction of lanthanides :

Depending on the concentration of lanthanides in sample solution, 1 to 5 ml aliquot (up to 250 µg) was taken in a separating funnel, 10 ml of 0.1% (w/v) 2,3-dihydroxynaphthalene (2,3-H₂ND) in ethyl acetate was added and swirled for 2 min. Then added 10 ml of 10% (w/v) sodium acetate, adjusted the pH of the solution at 6.0 by adding slowly diluted ammonium hydroxide and hydrochloric acid. Shaken for 3 min. After the phase separation, the organic layer was discarded and the aqueous layer was taken in another separating funnel, added 10 ml of 1.0% (w/v) 2,3-dihydroxynaphthalene (2,3-H₂ND) in ethylacetate and swirled for 2 min, then adjusted the pH of the solution to 9.0 by adding slowly diluted ammonium hydroxide/hydrochloric acid. Shaken for 3 min and allowed for phase separation. The organic layer was washed with distilled water in case of samples containing high iron. REEs in the organic phase was selectively stripped off at pH 6.3 ± 0.2. Stripped off REEs in the aqueous layer was taken in a 50 ml beaker for

color development. The process blank and standards were also run in exactly similar way as described for sample.

Spectrophotometric determination of REEs by arsenazo-III method :

In the 50 ml beaker containing extracted lanthanides, adjusted pH 2.6 ± 0.1 by adding slowly diluted ammonium hydroxide and hydrochloric acid. Then added 1 ml of 1% (w/v) meso tartaric acid solution and 1 ml of 0.1% (w/v) arsenazo-III solution. Transferred this into 25 ml volumetric flask and diluted to volume with distilled water and mixed. Measured the absorbance of the solution in a 1 cm quartz cell at 665 nm wavelength against a reagent blank.

Results and discussion

Owing to severe mutual interference of uranium, thorium, zirconium and REEs(T), none of these elements can be selectively estimated in the presence of others by the well known spectrophotometric reagent, arsenazo-III. Selective separation of these elements prior to their individual determination using this reagent is a must. As observed by us, no method of separation of these elements is as effective as the liquid-liquid extraction in terms of selectivity and rapidity of separation. The reagents commonly used for the separation of these elements viz. TBP, TOPO, D₂EHPA, MIBK, DMSO etc. are not very selective and have got their own limitations. In view of the above limitations, the authors present the results obtained by using the reagent, 2,3-dihydroxynaphthalene for the selective separation of rare earth elements from thorium and uranium. REEs are found to form a 1 : 3 neutral complex with the reagent, 2,3-dihydroxynaphthalene (2,3-H₂ND) in the pH range 8–12, whereas thorium forms 1 : 2 neutral complex²⁶ with this ligand in the pH range 5–12 in the absence of any counter cation like cetyltrimethylammonium ion (CTA⁺). These enable us to extract thorium at the pH 6 into a suitable organic solvent like ethyl acetate leaving uranium and REEs in the aqueous solution. REEs from this aqueous solution were then extracted at pH 9 into the same solvent leaving uranium in the aqueous solution. All these separations are depicted in Fig. 1. REEs is then back extracted selectively into aqueous solution at pH 6.3 ± 0.2 and then determined spectrophotometrically using arsenazo-III. Uranium in this condition is not extracted unless a counter cation (CTA⁺) is used at this pH.

Fig. 1. Effect of pH on the extraction of uranium, thorium, REEs and zirconium [U : 50 μ g, Th : 50 μ g, REEs : 50 μ g, Zr : 50 μ g and 2,3-H₂ND : 100 mg].

The variables affecting the liquid-liquid extraction of REEs have been systematically studied as follows :

(i) *Effect of pH on the extraction of REEs :*

The extraction of lanthanides as lanthanide-2,3-dihydroxynaphthalene (2,3-H₂ND) complex was studied over the pH range, 0 to 12. It has been observed that the extraction is not significant up to pH 8. Thereafter, the degree of extraction is complete and remains constant up to a pH of 12 or so. At pH 9 and above the extraction is more than 98%. The pH of 9 was easily attained using sodium acetate and a few drops of ammonia solution. Fig. 1 shows the percentage extraction of REEs against different pH at fixed concentration of the reagent 2,3-H₂ND.

(ii) *Effect of the reagent, 2,3-dihydroxynaphthalene concentration for the extraction of REEs :*

At the optimum pH of 9.0 of the aqueous medium, the concentration of the reagent 2,3-dihydroxynaphthalene (2,3-H₂ND) was varied over the range 10 to 300 mg per 10 ml of organic solvent. It was found that 100 mg of the reagent was sufficient to extract 300 μ g REEs. Fig. 2 shows the percentage extraction of REEs against varying concentration of the reagent, 2,3-H₂ND at pH 9.0. For best result a 10 ml of 1.0% 2,3-H₂ND in ethyl acetate was used for solvent extraction.

Fig. 2. Effect of reagent 2,3-H₂ND concentration (% w/v) on the extraction of REEs [REEs : 300 μ g, pH : 9, 10 ml of different 2,3-H₂ND concentration (%) have been used].

(iii) *Effect of electrolyte and equilibrium time on the extraction of REEs :*

As already discussed in the preceding section, a 1 : 3 complex of lanthanides and 2,3-H₂ND is formed over the pH range 8 to 12, and the extraction is almost complete above pH 9. No improvement was observed in the degree of extraction with the addition of electrolyte like NaCl, CaCl₂, Na₂SO₄, CH₃COONa etc. The use of CH₃COONa is restricted only for adjusting pH. As lanthanides form complexes with the reagent and no counter cation is required for the extraction of these complexes, this showed that the complexes are neutral in nature. This aspect was attested by evaporating the ethylacetate layer loaded with REEs-2,3-H₂ND complexes, destroying the organic fraction (2,3-H₂ND) by igniting the residue at 600 °C in a muffle furnace, dissolving the product in a few drops of HNO₃, and then determining Na in a flame photometer. No sodium was detected which demonstrates that no counter cation was required for the extraction of lanthanides. Fig. 3 shows the extraction behavior of lanthanides with varying concentration of electrolyte.

The equilibrium time required for complete extraction of the complex was 3 min.

(iv) *Choice of solvents :*

Various polar and non polar solvents were tried for

Fig. 3. Effect of electrolyte (sodium acetate) on the extraction of REEs [REEs : 50 μ g, 2,3- H_2 ND : 100 mg, extraction pH : 9].

liquid-liquid extraction of the complex. Mention may be made of butanol, *n*-butylacetate, ethylacetate, MIBK, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, hexane, benzene, toluene etc. The extraction was found to be facile and the distribution co-efficient was found maximum with ethylacetate.

(v) *Effect of stripping agents and stripping pH :*

The stripping agents used for completely transferring REEs from the ethylacetate phase to aqueous phase were HCl, H_2SO_4 , H_3PO_4 , HNO_3 and CH_3COOH . The best results i.e. almost complete transfer took place in the pH range 6.1 to 6.5 using CH_3COONa as a stripping agent. Above pH 6.5, stripping of lanthanides does not take place. Whereas, below pH 5.5, thorium and zirconium (if present in organic phase), get stripped off in to aqueous phase. Therefore, the optimum stripping pH for lanthanides was fixed as 6.3 ± 0.2 . Stripping studies were carried out by using 10% (w/v) aqueous solutions of sodium acetate having different pH over the range, 1 to 8 (pH were adjusted using dilute HCl/ NH_4OH). For best result, a 10 ml of 10% (w/v) aqueous solution of CH_3COONa having a pH ~ 5.9 was used as stripping solution. Fig. 4 shows the stripping pattern.

(vi) *Extraction equilibrium and tentative composition of the complexes :*

For the extraction of lanthanides, no counter cation was required. Lanthanides form a neutral complex with

Fig. 4. Effect of pH on the stripping of REEs using 10% (w/v) CH_3COONa as stripping solution [REEs : 50 μ g, 2,3- H_2 ND : 100 mg, extraction pH : 9].

2,3- H_2 ND. However, in order to ascertain the composition of the complex formed, curve fitting method was used. By plotting the logarithmic value of distribution ratio of $(REE)^{3+}$ vs experimental variables i.e. logarithmic concentration of 2,3-dihydroxynaphthalene in the organic phase, a slope of 3 was obtained indicating that 3 molecules of the ligand took part in the complex formation (Fig. 5). Possibility of the formation of ternary complex with acetate ion introduced into the solution from sodium acetate was ruled out because slope analysis with respect to CH_3COONa confirmed that CH_3COO^- ion did not take part in the complex formation (the slope was observed to be < 0.5).

Fig. 5. Plot of log D of La^{3+} -2,3-dihydroxynaphthalene complex vs log of initial molar concentration of 2,3- H_2 ND.

Similarly, the nature of the complex formed was also ascertained by analyzing Na⁺ ion in the organic extract by flame photometry. Negative test for Na⁺ indicated that unlike the previously studied system²⁵, it does not act as a counter cation. Except for Na⁺ ion, no other cation like CTA⁺ (cetyltrimethylammonium ion) was present in the solution for the extraction of the complex into ethylacetate. The extraction behavior of lanthanides in the absence of sodium acetate also confirmed that no counter cation is required. This clearly indicated that the complex formed is neutral in nature.

The mechanism by which total REEs (a mixture of individual rare earth elements) was extracted from an aqueous phase into ethylacetate by using 2,3-dihydroxynaphthalene (2,3-H₂ND) follows the reaction.

The equilibrium constant (*K*) of the reaction can be written as

$$K_{ex(w)} = \frac{[REE(HND)_w^{+(3-w)}] [H^+]^w}{[REE^{3+}] [H_2ND]^w} \quad (2)$$

$$K_{ex(w)} = D[H^+]^w/[H_2ND]^w \quad (3)$$

$$\text{where as } D = \frac{[REE(HND)_w^{+(3-w)}]}{[REE^{3+}]} \quad (4)$$

Eq. (3) can be written as,

$$\log K_{ex(w)} = \log D - w \text{ pH} - w \log [H_2ND] \quad (5)$$

Thus the stoichiometry of the complex is 1 : 3 (REE : 2,3-H₂ND). The empirical formula of the active species extracted is therefore, presumed to be [REE(HND)₃]. The complex formation of REE³⁺ with 2,3-H₂ND follow the following reaction.

Tentative structure of the complex :

(vii) Effect of diverse ions :

The pH of lanthanide extraction (pH 8–10) is so chosen that the elements which interfere in the determination of lanthanide when arsenazo-III is used as a spectropho-

tometric/colorimetric reagent for determination of lanthanides are eliminated while extracting lanthanides. At this pH, REEs and traces of thorium (if present, because most of thorium get extracted at pH 6 during first extraction) are extracted but REEs are selectively stripped off from thorium. Similarly, uranium which forms an anionic complex over the pH range 4–12, also does not get extracted at the conditions of REEs extraction²⁷. Zirconium which interferes in the spectrophotometric determination of lanthanides is extracted partially along with REEs, but is not stripped off alongwith lanthanides at the pH 6.3 ± 0.2. Moreover, it is masked with meso tartaric acid, if any traces of zirconium present in solution. Most of the silicate rock and soil samples contain negligible amount of zirconium. Fe, Cu and V are removed²⁴ while extracting out thorium at pH 6.0.

Effect of diverse ions in the determination of 1.0 µg ml⁻¹ REEs is shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Effect of diverse ions on the determination of 1.0 µg ml⁻¹ REEs

Sl. no.	Ions	Tolerance limit (µg ml ⁻¹)
1.	Fe ^a , Na ⁺ , K ⁺ , Ca ²⁺ , Mg ²⁺ , Rb, Sr, acetate ion, citrate ion	> 10,000
2.	UO ₂ ²⁺ , Th ^a	10,000
3.	Cu ^a , Ni, V ^a , Mo, Co, Zn Al, Cl ⁻ , NO ₃ ⁻ , PO ₄ ³⁻	1,000
4.	Zr ^b	100

^aBy extractive separation, ^bafter masking with tartaric acid.

Analytical application :

In order to validate the method developed and in order to attest the efficacy of the extractive system, the proposed method was thoroughly applied to synthetic mixtures, rock, soil samples and a few Certified Reference Materials. Results obtained are shown in Tables 2, 3 and 4. The results shown in the tables are self explanatory.

Table 2. Recovery of REEs by proposed method in synthetic mixtures, (n = 4)

Synthetic mixtures	U ₃ O ₈ (µg) added	Th (µg) added	REEs (µg) added	REEs (µg) found	% of recovery
S.M. 1	50	50	20	19.0	95
S.M. 2	50	50	50	48.5	97
S.M. 3	50	50	100	98.0	98

Table 3. Recovery studies of REEs by proposed method for SY/3, MRG-1, (n = 4)

Reference standards	REEs(T) (%) found by proposed method	Reported value (%)
SY/3	0.57	0.60
MRG-1	0.014	0.015

Table 4. Results of REEs obtained in rock samples using the proposed method and ICP-AES method, (n = 4)

(Samples received from North Singhbhum Mobile Belt, Purulia Dist. West Bengal, India)

Reference sample No.	REEs(T) (%) found by proposed method	REEs(T) (%) found by ICP-AES method
JCL-162	0.021	0.0223
JCL-176	0.014	0.0120
JCL-178	0.016	0.0157
JCL-189	<0.010	0.0070
JCL-191	<0.010	0.0093
JCL-215	0.024	0.0228

tory. The results show that the method developed is quite effective in the separation of REEs for its accurate determination by arsenazo-III method. The precision of the method is about 1 to 5% as RSD (n = 4) depending on the concentration of the analyte.

Conclusion

The extractive system developed is highly effective in the separation of traces to percentage level REEs (total) in various samples of diverse matrices such as rock, soil and sediment samples. By the application of the method, thorium, uranium and REEs can be easily separated from each other.

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